

Understanding and Developing Emotional Intelligence – An Empirical Study of Students in Hubli City

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is focusing on understanding and developing the emotional intelligence of Students in Hubli City. The emotional intelligence is the capability of individuals to recognize their own emotions and those of others, with the different feelings and label them appropriately. A sample size of 275 students were surveyed during the month of October & November 2019. Further, the data collected is then statistical techniques like One Way Anova and Factor Analysis, where One Way ANOVA is used for identifying the positive and negative attributes from the students and Factor analysis is used to determine the major important factors. The major conclusions drawn from this research is found to be that the students are aware of their Emotions, but they do not know how to manage emotions. As they are unable to trace their emotions patterns the students are found in position where they not handling the negative emotions about the self.

1. INTRODUCTION

The intelligence quotient, or IQ is an aspect derived from one of several different standardized tests to measure intelligence. It has been used to assess giftedness and sometimes underpin recruitment. Many have argued that IQ, or conventional intelligence, is too narrow concept. Some people are academically brilliant yet socially and interpersonally in built. We know that success does not automatically follow those who possess a high IQ rating. IQ sometimes can be built from experience and knowledge.

“If your emotional abilities aren’t in hand, if you don’t have self-awareness, if you are not able to manage your distressing emotions, if you can’t have empathy and have effective relationships, then no matter how smart you are, you are not going to get very far.” Daniel Goleman

Wider areas of intelligence enable us that how successful we are moral, toughness, determination, and vision help. But emotional intelligence, often measured as an emotional intelligence quotient, or EQ, is more and more relevant to important work-related outcomes such as individual performance, organizational productivity, Organisational goals. The core emotional competencies are Self-awareness, Social perception, Managing emotions, Empathy, Social skills.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The author says about in her critique of emotional intelligence theory, Waterhouse (2006) makes many claims regarding emotional intelligence. The argument starts with “many conflicting constructs of EI” saying that it is a valid concept and having different perception towards it.

Second argument author did research and suggests us that “EI has not been differentiated from personality plus IQ.” Third argument states that” the claim that EI determines real-world success has not been validated.” Lastly, she proposes that research on brain function proves that there cannot be a “unitary Emotional intelligence.”On this above critique she argues that EI competencies should not be thought in schools. (Extein, Melissa , Daniel , & Roger , 2010)

The present study of author explored Emotional Intelligence among male and female. The examination test was included one hundred and sixty subjects (N = 160) who were arranged in two gatherings. They were eighty guys (n = 80) and eighty females (n = 80) from N.W.F.P. Snowball inspecting system was utilized to choose subjects. Individual data sheet was utilized to acquire segment data. Emotional Quotient Inventory (EQ-I) was utilized to discover the degree of Emotional knowledge among the subjects. Gender orientation distinction in Emotional Remainder Inventory uncovers that Males have high emotional knowledge as contrast with females (t=4.522, p<.01). (AHMAD, HAYAT , & SHERAZ , 2009).

The point of the present paper is to investigate the connection between emotional insight and powerful initiative to assess the propensity of passionate control of the average workers both male and female at an administrative level in a private and open division of Pakistan primarily Banking segment. A study of 50 individuals is directed by conveying. Arbitrary inspecting method is utilized to answer the instrument of the investigation. SPSS programming was utilized to break down the information gathered dependent on graphic measurements (mean, standard deviation, rate. The outcome demonstrates that the connection between authority style and Emotional Intelligence is sure and critical. (Batool, 2013)

Research recommends that directors who utilize passionate insight in these circumstances — for example, by adequately controlling their feelings — might quicken their vocations. Paradoxically, administrators who don't practice passionate knowledge at the point when looked with similar chances and difficulties might have their professions slowed down. (Côté, 2017) Research recommends that directors who utilize enthusiastic insight in these circumstances for example, by successfully controlling their feelings might quicken their vocations. Paradoxically, supervisors who don't practice passionate knowledge at the point when looked with similar chances and difficulties might have their vocations slowed down. (Myers & Mary , 2005).

The paper looks at the effect of components of EI, identified with mindfulness, on self-other understanding and pioneer execution, and tries to explain past outcomes through exact upgrades. We follow the hypothesis of Yammarino and Atwater (1997) while using the methodological methodology of Sosik also, Megerian (1999). Nonetheless, where Sosik and Megerian (1999) utilized a specially appointed proportion of EI, we use the Emotional Quotient Inventory (EQI) (Bar-On, 1997). Further, we expand the examination of Sosik and Megerian by testing it on an enormous example in a non-military, fabricating research setting. (Bratton, Nancy , & F. William, 2011)

The motivation behind this study was to inspect whether mindfulness of administrators (characterized as understanding among self and other authority appraisals) would direct connections between (a) parts of passionate knowledge and transformational administration conduct, and (b) transformational authority conduct and administrative execution. Multisource

information was gathered from 63 directors (who reacted about their passionate insight and transformational authority conduct), 192 subordinates (who appraised their administrator's transformational authority conduct what's more, execution results), and 63 bosses of central chiefs (who appraised administrative execution). Results showed that connections between enthusiastic knowledge viewpoints, pioneer conduct, and execution changed as an element of mindfulness of directors. The pragmatic elements of these discoveries are examined. (SOSIK & LARA , 2000)

The paper speaks about different attributes in emotional intelligence which will help to understand and develop emotional intelligence. The different attributes are Self-awareness, Self-regulation. Self-motivation, Social awareness and social skills. (Serrat, 2017) The investigation was performed targeting looking over enthusiastic knowledge and its connection with the scholarly presentation of restorative science understudies. To gauge enthusiastic knowledge, the instrument EQ-I-survey was chosen. A sample comprised of two hundred and twenty-three (223) youthful understudies, 70 guys and 153 females, who took part in this examination by stratified examining. At first, they filled the segment information structure and afterward they evaluated themselves on EQ-I-test. There were critical contrasts in the enthusiastic insight scores by living space of understudies ($p < 0.01$). thinking about the low degree of enthusiastic knowledge among understudies the significant connection among all out and a few segments enthusiastic insight with scholarly execution, it appears to be significant take to passionate knowledge in to thought understudies psychological well-being improve and assist them with carrying out their responsibilities all the more effectively. (FallahzadehH, 2011)

The reason for the present examination is to explore the relations between parts of enthusiastic knowledge and understudies' scholarly accomplishment of High schools in Tehran city. The research method was descriptive. The examples included around 380 subjects, 180 young ladies and 200 young men understudies. Results demonstrated that there is noteworthy relationship between primary parts of enthusiastic knowledge including self-motivation, self-awareness, self-regulation, social consciousness, social skills and student's scholarly accomplishment. Likewise, there is an important contrast among male and female says about passionate insight about emotional intelligence. (Joibari & Niloufar, 2011).

The paper says about the gender orientation affected the way that logical issues, passionate knowledge and social abilities were connected, and a backwards connection was introduced between relevant issues and passionate insight ($r = 0.63$) and social abilities ($r = 0.38$) for females, while this relationship was less fortunate for males. By method for end, we express that logical issues relate to passionate knowledge what's more, social abilities in Secondary Education understudies, yet this relationship contrasts as per gender orientation. (Salavera, Pablo , & Pilar, 2018).

The outcomes demonstrated that restorative instruction has a negative impact the passionate insight. Males and females in this examination had the equivalent enthusiastic knowledge that recommends the social consequences for enthusiastic knowledge. (Vasefi, Mohammadreza, & Mahmood , 2018)

Research Gap: To identify the Emotional intelligence in students.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

1	Source of data	Primary and Secondary data.
2	Sample unit	Students studying in Post-Graduation Course at Hubli City
3	Sampling method	Convenience sampling
4	Sample Size	A total of 384 respondents were contacted, out of which 275 questionnaires returned during the period of October and November 2019
5	Research approach	Questionnaire was administered for Post-Graduation Students of the Hubli City
6	Statistical technique	SPSS
6	Statistical tool	ANOVA, Factor analysis.
7	Location	Hubli City
8	Research instrument	Structured Questionnaire

3. OBJECTIVES

- To understand the self-awareness competencies in students.
- To determine that the students can know and manage his emotions.
- To understand the social skills competencies in students.

DATA ANALYSIS

The researcher has studied the emotions of the students studying in Post-Graduation in Hubli City. Further the data so collected is been analysed using One Way ANOVA to determine the positive and negative attributes for the respondents.

TABLE NO 1 ONE-WAY ANOVA

		SUM OF SQUARES	DF	MEAN SQUARE	F	SIG.	REJECTED / ACCEPTED
3. Do I try to control my thoughts?	Between Groups	10.071	1	10.071	9.529	0.002	Accepted
	Within Groups	288.525	273	1.057			
	Total	298.596	274				
4. Do I think before I speak?	Between Groups	0.644	1	0.644	0.618	0.432	Rejected
	Within Groups	284.505	273	1.042			
	Total	285.149	274				
5. Do I learn from negative feedback?	Between Groups	0.014	1	0.014	0.01	0.919	Rejected
	Within Groups	358.728	273	1.314			
	Total	358.742	274				
6. Do I acknowledge others?	Between Groups	1.331	1	1.331	1.346	0.247	Rejected
	Within Groups	269.891	273	0.989			
	Total	271.222	274				
7. Do I have a balanced view of myself?	Between Groups	0.198	1	0.198	0.176	0.675	Rejected
	Within Groups	307.998	273	1.128			
	Total	308.196	274				
8. Do I listen for the message, and not just the words?	Between Groups	0.202	1	0.202	0.209	0.648	Rejected
	Within Groups	264.525	273	0.969			
	Total	264.727	274				
9. Am I authentic (Genuine)?	Between Groups	5.333	1	5.333	5.366	0.021	Accepted

	Within Groups	271.336	273	0.994			
	Total	276.669	274				
10. Do I show empathy?	Between Groups	1.498	1	1.498	1.454	0.229	Rejected
	Within Groups	281.171	273	1.03			
	Total	282.669	274				
11. Do I praise others?	Between Groups	6.098	1	6.098	6.878	0.009	Accepted
	Within Groups	242.069	273	0.887			
	Total	248.167	274				
12. Do I give helpful feedback?	Between Groups	0.005	1	0.005	0.005	0.944	Rejected
	Within Groups	250.817	273	0.919			
	Total	250.822	274				
13. Do I willingly apologize?	Between Groups	6.077	1	6.077	5.876	0.016	Accepted
	Within Groups	282.345	273	1.034			
	Total	288.422	274				
14. Do I forgive and forget?	Between Groups	0.104	1	0.104	0.096	0.757	Rejected
	Within Groups	296.383	273	1.086			
	Total	296.487	274				
15. Do I keep my commitments?	Between Groups	0.399	1	0.399	0.438	0.509	Rejected
	Within Groups	248.743	273	0.911			
	Total	249.142	274				
16. Do I know how to handle negative emotions?	Between Groups	0	1	0	0	0.998	Rejected
	Within Groups	302.385	273	1.108			
	Total	302.385	274				
17. Do I focus on what I can control?	Between Groups	6.539	1	6.539	8.546	0.004	Accepted
	Within Groups	208.901	273	0.765			
	Total	215.44	274				
18. Can I tell when others are using my emotions to manipulate or control me?	Between Groups	1.423	1	1.423	1.458	0.228	Rejected
	Within Groups	266.453	273	0.976			
	Total	267.876	274				

From the table 1, it is evident from the One Way Anova that, the Emotional intelligence attributes were positive or negative for respondents. The data is positive if <0.05 and it is negative >0.05 . (FallahzadehH, 2011) says in the research about positive and negative attribute of EI model.

FROM OUR RESEARCH WE CAN SAY THAT THE POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE ATTRIBUTES ARE

POSITIVES ATTRIBUTES FOR THE RESPONDENTS ARE AS FOLLOWS

- Do I try to control my thoughts.
- Am I authentic (Genuine).
- Do I praise others.
- Do I willingly apologize.
- Do I focus on what I can control.

NEGATIVE ATTRIBUTES FOR THE RESPONDENTS ARE AS FOLLOWS

- Do I think before I speak.

SELF-AWARENESS NOT THERE FOR THE RESPONDENTS SELF-AWARENESS CONTAINS THE FOLLOWING DOMAINS

- Emotional awareness: Recognizing one’s emotions and their effects.
- Accurate self-assessment: Knowing one’s strengths and limits.
- Self-confidence: Sureness about one’s self-worth and capabilities.

Further, the researcher wanted to understand the important factors, which help to understand the emotional intelligence of the students.

TABLE NO 2 ROTATED COMPONENT MATRIX

	COMPONENT		
	1	2	3
Do I try to control my thoughts?	.787		
Do I learn from negative feedback?	.678		
Am I authentic (Genuine)?	.586		
Do I have a balanced view of myself?	.554		
Do I think before I speak?	.531		
Do I acknowledge others?		.648	
Do I show empathy?		.633	
Do I give helpful feedback?		.614	
Do I praise others?		.595	
Do I know how to handle negative emotions?			.729
Do I focus on what I can control?			.663
Can I tell when others are using my emotions to manipulate or control me?			.651
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.			
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.			
a. Rotation converged in 3 iterations.			

The principal component analysis approach, using varimax rotation, reduced the explanatory variables in to 3 major factors based on the 12 values greater than 0.50. The criterion of factor loading was based on the absolute value of co-efficient in the Rotated Component Matrix. Each factor was composed of specific explanatory variables that loaded more than 0.50 on the factor. In the co-efficient display format option co-efficient with values less than 0.50 were suppressed. The variables were sorted by size under factor based on the absolute values of their loadings. The total variance explained by the factor analysis is calculated at 47.136. Of these factors **Self Awareness** has the maximum factors of five, **Empathy** has the second maximum factors which is four factors, and lastly **Self-Management** has three factors, each factor loading under each component.

4. CONCLUSION

From the research we conclude that the students of post-graduation can interpret their emotional pattern, namely the emotions like negative and positive emotions in different situations. Further researcher found from the study that the students who can understand their emotional pattern but are not in position to manage their own emotions.

By developing their emotional intelligence individuals can become more productive and successful at what they do, and help others become more productive and successful too. The process and outcomes of emotional intelligence development also contain many elements known to reduce stress—for individuals and understand their emotions —by moderating conflict; promoting understanding and relationships; and fostering stability, continuity, and harmony. Finally, it links strongly with concepts of love and spirituality.

Emotional intelligence will also help individual to manage the emotions. The elements are self-control, trustworthiness, conscientiousness(responsibility), adaptability and innovativeness. Self-regulation is a highly significant function in human life. It is concerned with how you control and manage yourself and your emotions, inner resources, and abilities. It also includes individual ability to manage your impulses. It also says about taking responsibility for your own actions and ensuring that what you do matches with your personal values.

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